

Smart Web Searches: Leveraging AI and Big Data for Personalization

Dheeraj Malhotra*¹ and Midhun Chakkravarthy²

¹Faculty of Computer Science Engineering, Lincoln University
College, Malaysia

²Faculty of Computer Science Engineering, Lincoln University
College, Malaysia

Abstract

Conventional search engines typically deliver the same set of output links to different users in response to the same search query, despite the variation in personalized search requirements among users. Additionally, the immense and continuously expanding nature of the web results in incomplete indexing, even by the most popular search engines. This paper addresses these issues by proposing a cloud architecture for a Meta search tool implemented through the Hadoop framework. Furthermore, current research work is extended from our previous work by incorporating ethical implications of personalized search. The extensive experimental evaluation shows that this proposed Meta search framework can surpass popular search engines in personalized search precision.

Keywords

Web Search Personalization, Hadoop-Map Reduce, Cloud Computing, AMSS, Big Data Analytics, Meta Search Engine, HDFS

Introduction

Search engines are critical for retrieving information from the web. Traditional search engines employ conventional mining approaches to extract meaningful page re-ranking patterns for web search personalization. However, in the era of Big Data, these traditional page ranking techniques are insufficient to meet modern user needs. Big Data refers to a vast collection of datasets that are extremely challenging to process using traditional data mining techniques. The Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) based computing framework can be utilized to extract useful page re-ranking patterns. This research introduces an innovative cloud-based approach to enhance the capabilities of the previously proposed IMSS tool. The Advanced Meta Search System (AMSS) leverages Google Cloud Platform and the HDFS framework to interpret personalized search requirements of the end-user, re-ranking web pages retrieved from various search engines within the backend of the AMSS tool to best match the user's search requisites.

Research Problem and Objectives of Research

Web information retrieval involves searching and finding unstructured web documents to fulfill individual information needs from an enormous collection on the World Wide Web (WWW). A retrieval system must search for relevant documents among billions available on the WWW. Users of traditional information retrieval systems were technically adept at phrasing search

queries. However, modern users rarely use correct spellings, specific keywords, or operators while searching. They expect features like auto-complete from search engines. Additionally, search engines are more frequently used by ordinary people, including those who are not literate, rather than just IT professionals. Most search engines adopt a "One Size Fits All" approach by listing similar links in the same order for a given search query. The primary objectives of this research are to design and develop a meta search tool known as Advanced Meta Search System (AMSS), with features such as:

- A focus on personalized precision in web retrieval rather than recall.
- A user-friendly interface to easily access the features of the proposed meta search tool on Google Cloud Platform for Big Data Analytics
- Ethical implications of personalized web search should be considered while implementing personalized web search

Big data analytics is crucial for a meta search tool like the proposed AMSS. The number of web pages retrieved by backend search engines within a meta search tool needs to be analyzed to generate an accurate page ranking order in real time to satisfy the end-user. The vast amount of data retrieved from various search engines can be efficiently analyzed using Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) when deployed on the Google Cloud Platform (GCP). GCP is used to set up a multi-node cluster required to implement a meta search engine like AMSS. Moreover, GCP provides a suitable platform for various cloud services. The GCP module for implementing Virtual Machines (VMs) allows developers to choose VMs with varying configurations in terms of cores, memory, and OS images, best matching the end-users' requirements.

Architecture of Proposed System

The architecture of the proposed system includes several critical components, which are discussed as follows:

Name Node (NN): Acts as the master node in HDFS, directing all slave Data Nodes. It is responsible for tracking the system's health and enabling faster access from RAM by maintaining file system metadata.

Secondary Name Node (SNN): Unlike the NN, SNN does not track changes made to HDFS but maintains journaling for incremental updates within the metadata.

Cloud Manager: Serves as the supervisor of the proposed architecture, enabling inter-cluster communication, and appropriate storage distribution among Data Nodes.

Data Node (DN): Considered a slave node, it is responsible for storing data. When a write/read operation on an HDFS file is required, the file is divided into blocks, each stored in a specific DN as decided by the NN.

Job Tracker (JT): Acts as a communication link between the NN and the client (Map-Reduce application), responsible for accepting expanded search query requests from the client and allocating tasks to various Task Trackers on the Data Nodes.

Task Tracker (TT): Accepts search query requests from the JT, collects page links returned by corresponding search engines, and sorts those links to match the user's priorities. This comprehensive architecture ensures efficient processing and personalization of search queries, addressing the limitations of traditional search engines and improving search precision to meet modern users' needs effectively.

The encrypted cluster storage ensures privacy of data depicting personalized preferences of a particular user, as cloud storage usually possesses the challenges of various serious security concerns, however algorithms used by proposed tool ensures encryption of data before storage on cloud cluster.

Fig.1. Proposed Architecture of AMSS

3.1. Cloud Cluster Configuration of Meta Search Tool

There are two possible ways to set up a cluster on Google cloud:

- Single Node Configuration
- Multi-Node Configuration

The step by step configuration for a metasearch application is discussed below. The node configuration will first create a VM instance known as a master instance. The master instance will serve the purpose of both the name node and data node. However, slave instances will act as data nodes to process the links returned by background search engines. The common steps for master and slave instance setup for IMSS tool are listed as follows:

- Java Installation
- Hadoop Installation
- Configuring Environment Variables
- Configuring.XML Files
- Creating Directories and Changing Ownership
- Rebooting
- RSA Key Generation and Authorization
- Name Node Cleaning and Service Verification
- Firewall Rules Settings
- DFS Health Checkup

The above steps are required for a single node setup. However, the additional steps required for a multi-node cluster are listed as follows:

- Networking and SSH Syncing
- Editing Masters and Slaves File
- Property Modification in .XML Files

The name node and data node directories are first required to be deleted and then recreated. This recreation is required to avoid any possibility for junk data within these directories and hence to facilitate multi-node configuration and can be accomplished through the execution of commands. The master instance is responsible for directing all slave instances with web page links as returned by the number of background search engines to the metasearch tool. The master instance is also responsible for HDFS book-keeping tasks and monitoring the overall health of the cluster. The master instance is required to remain active all the time as failure or pause of the master instance will make the entire cluster inaccessible and hence the breakdown of the AMSS application. The number of duplicate copies kept on different slave instances is determined by the replication factor. The master instance will keep track of all slave instances via a heartbeat connection. A daemon called Job Tracker (JT) on the master instance is responsible for accepting expanded search query requests from the client and allocating those tasks to Task Trackers (TT) residing on different slave instances. The JT can also reallocate the job to a new TT on the replica of a slave instance in case of a failure of a node to ensure that slave failure does not lead to the cluster breakdown or job failure. The TT is active on slave instance, unlike JT which is active on a master instance. TT and JT both are known as computing nodes. Besides, TT is also required to update its existing status to JT via heartbeat connection. The responsibility of a TT here in the cluster is to accept the search query request from a JT and to collect the page links returned by a corresponding search engine and to sort those links according to personalized preferences of the user. However, to reduce the communication time between master and slave processes, AMSS application is deployed as a single node cluster setup. The proposed instance used as master cum slave instance in IMSS project to deploy single node cluster setup for metasearch application in the current research work is shown in figure 2.

3.1. Cloud Cluster Configuration of Meta Search Tool

There are two ways to configure a cluster on Google Cloud: Single Node Configuration and Multi-Node Configuration. Below is a step-by-step guide for setting up a metasearch application. Initially, a VM instance known as the master instance is created. This master instance functions as both the name node and data node. On the other hand, slave instances serve as data nodes processing links returned by background search engines. The common steps for setting up both master and slave instances for the IMSS tool include: installing Java, installing Hadoop, configuring environment variables, configuring .XML files, creating directories and changing ownership, rebooting, generating and authorizing RSA keys, cleaning the name node and verifying services, setting firewall rules, and performing a DFS health check.

For a single-node setup, these steps suffice. However, for a multi-node cluster, additional steps are required, such as networking and SSH syncing, editing the masters and slaves file, and modifying properties in .XML files. It is necessary to delete and recreate the name node and data node directories to prevent any junk data and facilitate multi-node configuration. This is achieved through the execution of commands.

The master instance directs all slave instances, distributing web page links returned by background search engines to the metasearch tool. It is also responsible for HDFS bookkeeping tasks and monitoring the cluster's overall health. The master instance must remain continuously active since any failure or pause would render the entire cluster inaccessible, causing the AMSS application to break down. The replication factor determines the number of duplicate copies kept on different slave instances, with the master instance tracking all slave instances via a heartbeat connection.

A daemon called Job Tracker (JT) on the master instance accepts expanded search query requests from the client and allocates tasks to Task Trackers (TT) on various slave instances. JT can also reassign jobs to a new TT on a replica of a slave instance if a node fails, ensuring that slave failures do not lead to cluster breakdown or job failure. TT is active on slave instances, unlike JT which is active on the master instance. Both TT and JT are computing nodes. TT must also update its status to JT via a heartbeat connection. In the cluster, TT accepts search query requests from JT, collects page links returned by corresponding search engines, and sorts those links according to the user's personalized preferences.

To minimize communication time between master and slave processes, the AMSS application is deployed as a single-node cluster setup. The proposed instance, used as both the master and slave instance in the IMSS project, deploys a single-node cluster setup for the metasearch application, as depicted in Figure 2. This configuration effectively addresses the requirements of personalized web search, ensuring high efficiency and reliability in processing vast amounts of data returned by various search engines.

This detailed configuration process enables the AMSS tool to leverage cloud computing and big data analytics effectively, offering personalized and precise search results that outperform traditional search engines in terms of user satisfaction. Through efficient cluster management and resource allocation, the proposed system ensures high availability and fault tolerance while significantly enhancing the scalability and performance of web search personalization efforts. By harnessing the robust capabilities of Google Cloud Platform and the Hadoop framework, the AMSS tool represents a significant advancement in the field of meta search engines, addressing the ever-growing challenges of web search personalization in the Big Data era.

Fig.2. Single-node cluster setup of proposed Meta Search tool on GCP

Deploying the Advanced Meta Search System (AMSS) tool on a Cloud platform backed by second-generation Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) offers several advantages:

Elastic Scaling: Virtual machine instances created to run the AMSS application can be added or removed based on the load. The number of web links returned by background search engines determines the number of data nodes used by the application, a process known as dynamic scaling.

Resource Management: The meta search application is installed on Google Cloud Platform (GCP), which provides the necessary virtual machine instances, network bandwidth, and other infrastructure. In case of unexpected failures or hardware updates, GCP automatically allocates new VMs for the IMSS application, saving considerable effort in IT and hardware skills required to deploy and manage the application.

Infrastructure Offloading: Using GCP significantly reduces the costs associated with managing one's own data center, hardware infrastructure, network bandwidth,

and software licensing. GCP helps minimize infrastructural costs and supports pay-on-demand, making it a cost-effective solution.

Handling Search Load Spikes: The number of users of the proposed application may unexpectedly increase on specific days. GCP-based second-generation HDFS deployment is ideal for scaling out during peak loads, handling load spikes in a user and developer-friendly manner.

High Reliability: GCP-based second-generation HDFS maintains redundant copies of data by keeping the same data in multiple Data Nodes (DNs). This strategy, known as "Rack Placement Strategy," ensures that the first copy is placed randomly in any rack, the second copy on a different rack, and the third copy on the same rack but in a different DN. This redundancy ensures high availability even in the case of a data node failure.

Reduced Operational Issues: With GCP's backup and reliable second-generation HDFS, the proposed tool will experience fewer operational issues. Professional Google experts maintain the network and software infrastructure, ensuring high availability and reliability of the AMSS tool for end users.

These advantages highlight the benefits of leveraging cloud computing and big data analytics for deploying the AMSS tool, ensuring efficient, reliable, and scalable web search personalization.

3.2 System Design of Proposed Meta Tool

The proposed Advanced Meta Search System (AMSS), as illustrated in Figure 3, is designed to allow users to select backend search engines based on their requirements. After entering the necessary search string, the tool lists all the shortlisted links retrieved through these backend search engines. Each link includes a stamp indicating the search engine from which it was retrieved. Additionally, various precision parameters, such as response time and security, are displayed alongside the search results. These parameters assist users in further shortlisting links to navigate and find the most relevant information. This functionality ensures that users receive tailored search results that meet their specific needs, enhancing both the efficiency and effectiveness of their search experience. Search Encryption tab on the interface of tool could be to enhance the protection of user sensitive data related to personalization including his/her search queries, so user need not to worry about retrieval of his/her personalized preferences while surfing the web.

Advance Meta Search System			
Select Tabs for Retrieval of Web Pages			
BING	YAHOO	GOOGLE	
Search String: Mapreduce Hadoop in HDFS			
Search Encryption	Web Search	Exit	
Page Ranking Box.....			
Rank	Links with Engine Stamp	Privacy	Time
1	https://Apache_Hadoop//mapreduce(G)	HTTPS:	15ms
2	www.cloudera.com//hdfs/hadoop2 (Y)	SSL	32ms
3	www.gttibm.org/datacom/software(B)	SSL	37ms

Fig.3. Proposed Interface of AMSS Tool

3.3 Experimental Verification and Graphical Analysis of Result

To evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of our proposed tool, we used trending query sets from Google Zeitgeist. We considered the top links on the first three pages retrieved from backend search engines, as users typically visit only the top links in search results. We determined various parameters that contribute to search precision for each web page retrieved by the AMSS tool. These parameters include the presence of a secure link, response time, page size, and the frequency of page content updates to ensure user satisfaction during web searches. These parameters are stored corresponding to each user in encrypted form to secure the privacy of end user while implementing web search personalization.

$$N_{IJ} = (MAX(P_{IJ}) - P_{IJ}) / (MAX(P_{IJ}) - MIN(P_{IJ}))$$

Where, P_{IJ} = Assessment of J_{th} Parameter of I_{th} retrieved page; N_{IJ} = Normalized assessment of J_{th} Parameter of I_{th} page; MIN, MAX = Minimum and Maximum value of Precision Parameter.

Fig.4. Search Precision Comparison of Proposed Meta Tool with Search Engines

This normalization process ensures that all parameters are on a comparable scale, facilitating accurate and meaningful analysis of the performance of our AMSS tool. Through this rigorous evaluation method, we can objectively measure the tool's ability to provide precise and personalized search results, enhancing the overall user experience. The graphical analysis of the normalized parameters will further illustrate the tool's effectiveness, providing clear insights into its capabilities and areas for potential improvement. In the next step, weighted precision of each candidate page is determined using equation $WP_I = \sum W_J \cdot N_{IJ}$, Where, WP_I = weighted precision of I_{th} page; W_J = Weight value assigned to J_{th} parameter based on the importance as determined by User ; where W_J lies between 0 and 1. The minimum value of precision parameter obtained among all calculated values should be considered as precision of proposed tool i.e. **Precision (Meta Tool) = MIN (WP_I)**. The proposed Meta search tool reports improved precision when compared with other popular search engines as shown in Fig.4.

Conclusion

The current research introduces an HDFS framework-based cloud architecture for a Meta search tool, known as the Advanced Meta Search System (AMSS), aimed at enhancing web search personalization. The effectiveness of the AMSS was evaluated by comparing its weighted search precision against popular search engines. Results clearly indicated that the proposed approach effectively meets users' personalized search requirements. Future enhancements could involve integrating cognitive technologies into the design and development of Meta search tools to further refine and improve personalized precision. This potential for expansion underscores the promising capabilities of the AMSS in the evolving landscape of web search technologies.

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